

MANUFACTURING OF HYBRID STRUCTURES BY PREPREG PRESS TECHNOLOGY

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Keywords: *Lightweight design, Multi-material system, Hybrid structure, Fiber reinforced plastic, Prepreg, Prepreg press technology, Forming of prepregs*

Abstract

Current research work at the Chair for Automotive Lightweight Construction (LiA) at the University of Paderborn concentrates on the investigation of hybrid materials and their processing. In particular, new manufacturing processes like the prepreg press technology are developed to make hybrid components attractive and available for automotive mass production. This includes for example the trimming of process chains, the decrease of cycle times and thus a reduction of process steps and costs. In addition, various combinations of hybrid materials are examined based on material and component tests.

First, the available paper will show basic technological investigations in the field of prepreg press technology. This technology can be used to manufacture sheet metal-CFRP-structures for automotive applications. The process is divided into four steps: After the combination of different prepreg layers and cutting, the semi-finished products are inserted into a heated mold. In this step the prepreg is directly pressed onto a formed sheet metal structure and pre-cured. The bonding is realized through the epoxy resin as an adhesive. In the next step the components are removed and stacked. The post-curing of the FRP-structure is realized in an anyway downstream cathoretic dip painting process. With expected cycle times of less than five minutes, the developed approach for manufacturing locally reinforced components is one possibility to solve the challenges of high-volume manufacturing in the field of CFRP.

After giving an overview of the process of manufacturing multi-material components by using sheet metal and FRP prepregs research results regarding tool design, process and forming parameters as well as process control and cycle times will be discussed.

1 Introduction

Due to economic and ecologic constraints the development of lightweight concepts becomes extremely important. For example, on the one hand the maximum average CO₂ emissions of automotive manufacturer's vehicle fleets are regulated by the European Commission. On the other hand aspects like fuel consumption have to be regarded concerning limited natural resources and running costs.

Nevertheless, the average weight of automobiles increased over the past years by about 100 kg per decade. This is mainly a result of rising comfort and safety requirements. To reverse this trend, the automotive industry identified lightweight design as a key factor.

2 State of the Art

2.1 Automotive Lightweight Construction

In automotive lightweight construction three main trends are obvious: lightweight design is realized by using high-strength metal alloys, by substituting for example metals for composites, or by combining different materials.

Using high-strength metal alloys offers the opportunity to reduce the wall thickness of structures. However, once a critical minimum thickness is reached, designers can expect stability problems. Thus, the potential of high-strength materials for light weight construction is limited.

Second, substituting conventional construction materials with carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) allows considerable weight savings [1] [2] of about 50 % compared to current solutions. At the moment FRP-structures are predominantly used for

high-priced vehicles. Main challenges for the automotive industry are to reduce high costs of processing these materials, manufacturing FRP-structures and to integrate FRP into existing processes.

Hence, structural components realized in multi-material design are an interesting alternative. They consist of a combination of, for example, steel and FRP [3] [4]. Two approaches can be distinguished. The high stiffness of the so called “Erlanger Beam” is achieved by reinforcing a thin-walled steel structure with short fiber reinforced plastic ribs by means of form closure. Depending on the vehicle, this method can save between 0.3 kg and 0.5 kg only in the roof frame [5]. The second approach constitutes a combination of ultra-high-strength steels and continuous fiber reinforced plastics. In order to increase the overall strength of the components, steel and FRP are bonded tightly across a large area. This design should allow manufacturers to produce safety-relevant vehicle components, such as B-pillars, at lower costs compared to a mere CFRP design. Using such material for a B-pillar, 6 kg per vehicle or up to 35 % of the weight could be saved [6] [7]. Due to the tight bonding between both single materials, these are also called hybrid materials.

2.2 Challenges of Multi-Material-Structures

One main disadvantage of today’s multi-material systems is among other things the manufacturing. This is predominantly manual or only partially automated. The three most commonly used joining methods are welding [8], riveting [9] and bonding [10]. All of them necessitate an additional time and cost consuming process step. These disadvantages shall be overcome with the production of hybrid materials by the prepreg press technology and the use of the matrix resin as an adhesive. Thus, multi-material components of highest strength can be produced in large volumes.

3 Sheet Metal-FRP-Hybrid Structures

Current research work at the Chair for Automotive Lightweight Construction (LiA) at the University of Paderborn concentrates on the investigation of hybrid materials, their processing and their mechanical properties.

Hybrid materials consist of a sheet metal basic layer, a locally applied FRP reinforcement layer and an optional sheet metal covering layer. The layered structure offers the possibility to tailor components to their expected loading (Fig. 1). Such tailored structures do not only bear a high potential for lightweight design but also show an optimized use of the expensive FRP materials, which finally leads to cost-optimized lightweight constructions. The sandwich structure of hybrid materials increases the stiffness especially of area measured components. Due to the FRP reinforcements, the wall thickness of the steel parts can be reduced. Hybrid components can easily be integrated into existing processes of vehicle production, because their metallic surface enables the use of conventional joining technologies like spot welding or clinching. The integration into existing body constructions is also possible.

Fig. 1 Load adapted hybrid structure

4 Prepreg Press Technology

The prepreg press technology is one approach to produce hybrid structural automotive parts in large volumes. The process can be divided into four main parts (Fig. 2). First, prepregs (pre-impregnated, semi-finished fiber products) are produced continuously on special machines and shipped on coils. The layer structure is realized according to the expected loads in the component, for example a B-pillar. The laminate is cut corresponding to the expected structure geometry. Second, a robot handles the prepregs. After inserting an already formed steel structure into a heated steel tool, the prepreg is applied to the steel structure by automated handling. Then the tailored prepreg is pressed onto the sheet metal by a heated punch. As the epoxy

resin functions as an adhesive the joining of sheet metal and CFRP is realized in this third step, too. After a pre-curing of about 90 to 120 seconds at a temperature of 180 °C, depending on the thickness of the prepreg, the hybrid component is removed by a robot and stacked. The post-curing of the components is realized during a downstream cataphoretic painting process.

Fig. 2 Process run of prepreg press technology

5 Process Parameters

The process parameters have a great influence on the mechanical properties and the quality of the manufactured structures. Aside, the process parameters also influence the cycle times and thus the cost of the process. Several investigations on this topic have been accomplished.

5.1 Materials and experimental setups

The samples for the investigations consisted of sheet metal and CFRP. For the metal component a S235JR with a thickness of $t = 2$ mm was used. The prepregs were standard semi-finished products from SGL. The epoxy resin from SGL (Type E201) embeds carbon fibers in a symmetric 9 layer scrim (90/0₂/90/0)_s. The prepregs were manufactured by prepreg press technology as described in chapter 4. For the bonding with epoxy resin as an adhesive, the prepreg was directly pressed on the metallic surface.

The manufacturing process was divided into several steps. First, prepregs, sheet metal and release film were cut and layered. Second, the press process was realized. For this step different defined parameters were used. The test plates were post-cured in a furnace for 30 minutes at a temperature of 180 °C, which simulates the cataphoretic painting process. Next, three point bending samples were cut from the test plates and tested with a three point bending setup.

5.2 Results

During the experimental investigations, different combinations of temperature, pressure and time for the consolidation process were used. The aim was to identify a suitable process window to minimize the cycle times of the prepreg press process.

In Figure 3 the results of three point bending tests for different process parameters are illustrated. As a consolidation pressure 0.3 MPa was used. It can be seen that the values for the maximum bending stress achieve a plateau of about 750 MPa for pre-curing times above 60 seconds and temperatures above 160 °C. The values decrease at temperatures higher than about 190 °C.

Fig. 3 Results of three point bending tests for different process parameters

Figure 4 shows different micro sections and fiber volume contents of samples manufactured with

varying process parameters. Especially the pressure has a decisive influence on the fiber volume content. For a pressure between 0.2 and 0.4 MPa the provided fiber volume content of about 60 % is achieved. The pre-curing time and the temperature have nearly no influence on this characteristic.

Nevertheless the quality of the laminate finds an optimum at 180 °C and 90 seconds. In figure 5 benchmarks regarding pores, imperfections, waviness and layer thickness for different process parameters are listed.

			0.1 MPa	0.2 MPa	0.4 MPa	0.6 MPa
160 °C	60 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 55.96 \%$	$\varphi = 57.30 \%$	$\varphi = 58.87 \%$	$\varphi = 67.27 \%$
	90 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 56.77 \%$	$\varphi = 60.40 \%$	$\varphi = 60.62 \%$	$\varphi = 64.74 \%$
180 °C	60 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 55.09 \%$	$\varphi = 62.95 \%$	$\varphi = 64.83 \%$	$\varphi = 65.73 \%$
	90 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 55.62 \%$	$\varphi = 56.77 \%$	$\varphi = 63.26 \%$	$\varphi = 67.85 \%$
200 °C	60 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 56.56 \%$	$\varphi = 55.61 \%$	$\varphi = 62.64 \%$	$\varphi = 65.62 \%$
	90 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 55.70 \%$	$\varphi = 55.56 \%$	$\varphi = 61.80 \%$	$\varphi = 66.40 \%$

*FVC - Fiber volume content (Mean value of five measurement points)

Fig. 4 Micro sections and fiber volume content of different samples

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			0.1 MPa	0.2 MPa	0.4 MPa	0.6 MPa
160 °C	60 s	Small pores	o	o	o	o
		Large pores	+	+	+	o
		Other imperfections	o	o	+	+
		Low waviness	+	+	o	o
		Equal layer thickness	+	+	o	o
	90 s	Small pores	-	-	o	o
		Large pores	+	+	+	o
		Other imperfections	o	o	o	o
		Low waviness	+	+	o	o
		Equal layer thickness	+	+	+	+
180 °C	60 s	Small pores	-	o	o	o
		Large pores	+	+	o	o
		Other imperfections	o	o	+	+
		Low waviness	+	o	o	o
		Equal layer thickness	+	o	o	o
	90 s	Small pores	-	o	+	+
		Large pores	+	+	+	+
		Other imperfections	o	o	+	+
		Low waviness	+	o	o	o
		Equal layer thickness	+	+	o	o
200 °C	60 s	Small pores	-	-	o	o
		Large pores	+	+	+	+
		Other imperfections	o	o	+	+
		Low waviness	+	+	o	o
		Equal layer thickness	+	o	o	o
	90 s	Small pores	-	-	+	+
		Large pores	+	+	+	+
		Other imperfections	o	o	+	+
		Low waviness	o	o	o	o
		Equal layer thickness	+	o	o	o

(+) Good/less (o) Middle/average and (-) Poor/many

Fig. 5 Benchmark regarding pores, imperfections, waviness and layer thickness at different process parameters

Summarizing, optimal process parameters for the prepreg press process were found: the temperature for low cycle times should be about 180 °C, the pressure should be between 0.3 and 0.4 MPa and the time should be above 90 seconds. These values depend on influence factors such as the layer thickness, the materials or the textile semi-finished component.

6 Tool Concepts

In order to reduce the costs for producing hybrid components using prepreg press technology and to increase the component quality, it is necessary to have a near-to-final contour production for fiber composite structures to get by without elaborate and expensive post processing. To achieve this goal, four different tool concepts were developed and investigated to their suitability as prepreg press tools: a dip edge tool, a squish edge tool, a tool with a silicone sealant and a tool with a sealing frame (Fig. 6). In order to minimize the costs of tool production, the tests were first carried out on sheet molds.

When the two mold halves of the dip edge tool are being closed, the punch dips into the die, such that the tool is sealed in the opening direction before the actual press process takes place. The dip edge of the tool, which provides effective resistance to the flow front, is responsible for sealing. In the squish edge tool, this function is performed by a squish edge, which is obtained by engraving areas in the die and the punch. Epoxy resin that passes through this gap is squeezed by the squish edge, which leads to the sealing of the mould cavity. The resulting burr causes a higher rework. Using a silicone sealant in the third tool concept inhibits the lateral squeezing of the reinforcing fibres and the matrix resin. The sealing frame concept relies on sealing the mould parting line with the aid of a frame. The sealing frame is guided by the punch and centred by merging 40° chamfers. The die is designed as a plateau in order to facilitate the placement and the removal of the prepregs from the mould.

Fig. 6 Tool concepts investigated for producing near-to-final contour hybrid structures

In order to verify the functionality of the four tool concepts, various experimental studies were performed. For the production of the test plates, a consolidation temperature of 180 °C and a consolidation time of 5 minutes were used. The consolidation pressure was set at 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 and 1.0 N/mm². As a reference tool for investigated the tool concepts, a sheet mold was used. The investigations have shown that all the developed tool concepts are able to reproduce the reference contour

precisely (Fig. 6). The gap between the punch and the die in combination with an increasing pressure results in a burr with the tool concepts. The burr was easy to remove. At this point, the results can be improved through tighter tolerances or the use of a release film. Moreover, it was shown that the pore content in the CFRP decreases significantly with increasing pressure (Fig. 7). The layer structure was not affected by this and a constant layer thickness was achieved as well as a constant fiber distribution. It can be concluded from the microscopic examinations that the consolidation pressure for an almost pore-free laminate should be about 0.3 to 0.6 MPa.

Fig. 7 Results for the dip edge tool concept

The sealing frame concept has a high potential to transfer the results to a real geometry, like a locally reinforced B-pillar. In addition, this concept is suitable for a high-volume manufacturing and a high degree of automation. The sealing frame can also act as a blank holder in more complex geometries so as to achieve a defined material prepreg feed during the forming process. In order to compensate the tolerances, a silicone sealant can be applied to the frame.

7 Influence of the geometry

One further aspect of the investigations is related to the influence of different geometries on the quality of prepreg forming. For this, several test geometries have been investigated, such as hemisphere-, cup-, U-, hat- or B-pillar-geometries (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 Different test geometries for investigations on prepreg press technology

The prepreg press process allows a manufacturing of these structures. The unidirectional layer structure comes up against limits with increasing complexity, which results in a required subsequent trim of the components. Nevertheless the areas of activity could be realized without significant quality losses. Wrinkling could be detected in the boundary areas.

8 Conclusions

Hybrid structures consisting of sheet metal and fibre reinforced plastics offer a huge potential for lightweight design in the automotive industry. The prepreg press technology allows a significant reduction of the process steps as well as the process

time. By using prepreg press technology CFRP prepregs are formed into steel structures.

In this paper investigations on the process parameters and their influence on the laminate quality as well as on the fibre volume content were illustrated. Optimal process parameters have been found for the used boundary conditions. It has been shown that cycle times well below five minutes are achievable. Furthermore tool concepts for a near-to-final contour manufacturing of hybrid structures have been illustrated. In the end the influence of different geometries has been discussed. The prepreg press technology can be used to realize different component geometries.

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